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(Reptilia: Squamata: Varanidae)
with new designations
of a neotype and a lectotype**

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Catalog of the Genus *Varanus* (Reptilia: Squamata: Varanidae) with new designations of a neotype and a lectotype

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ABSTRACT

Most of the descriptive taxonomy of the genus *Varanus* pre-dates the introduction of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICSN) making the tracking of types a tedious effort. This catalog is an effort to fill a void in the taxonomy of the varanids by providing a list of the extant taxa, abbreviated synonymy, type specimens, type localities and relevant literature citations as far as is currently known. Type locality errors for several species are corrected. New lectotype and neotype specimens have been designated for *V. salvator celebensis* and *V. kordensis* respectively.

KEY WORDS

Monitor lizards; *Varanus*; types; type localities; distribution; new neotype; new lectotype.

INTRODUCTION

Varanid lizards have fascinated herpetologists for a long time. Monitors are different from most other lizards, possessing some anatomical and physiological characteristics more closely resembling birds and mammals than other lizards (De Lisle, 1996). The Varanidae are a family of lizards of some 70 species placed in a single genus, *Varanus*. Varanids are characterized by having well-developed pentadactyl limbs, movable eyelids, circular pupils, a visible external ear opening and a long, slender, deeply forked tongue. The family ranges from Africa to southern Asia, the Indo-Australian Archipelago, New Guinea, Australia and into the western Pacific islands. Monitors are primarily active, diurnal predators, although many also feed on carrion and a few eat fruit.

Although there have been many checklists of the genus *Varanus* (Mertens, 1963; Böhme, 2003; many websites), there has never been a list that includes both type localities and type specimens for all species. Cogger et al. (1983) provided a catalog (now 25 years old) of Australian species, but no such catalog exists for the entire genus. There is a need for an accurate compendium for the family Varanidae, identifying the type specimens for all validly published species names. A number of types that were “unknown” or thought to be lost have been rediscovered while previously unpublished details are provided for others. New type specimens (lectotype and neotype) are designated for *V. salvator celebensis* and *V. kordensis* respectively.

TAXONOMY

Keeping in mind the famous quote of Harold Cogger, “Taxonomy is a matter of opinion” (Golay, et al, 1993) based, of course, on the evaluation of the best evidence, the taxonomy used herein is my evaluation and I accept full responsibility for its use. The taxonomy used here is for the most part that found in Böhme (2003), with the following exceptions:

- 1) I recognize *V. beccarii* and *V. flavirufus* as full species.

- 2) There have been six new species described since Böhme's publication: *V. boehmei*, *V. bushi*, *V. lirungensis*, *V. rainerguentheri*, *V. reisingeri* and *V. zorum*.
- 3) I have adopted most of the recommendations of Koch et al. (2007) in their revision of the *V. salvator* complex.

This catalog is alphabetically ordered on the current species name, followed by the author and year of description. Type localities are those in the original description, except those in obvious error or those amended subsequently by authoritative sources.

Abbreviations of museums holding the types are as follows:

AMNH – American Museum of Natural History, New York, NY, U.S.A.
AMS (AM) – Australian Museum, Sydney, Australia
ANSP – Academy of Natural Sciences, Philadelphia, PA, U.S.A.
BMNH (BM) – Natural History Museum, London, United Kingdom
CM – Carnegie Museum, Pittsburgh, PA, U.S.A.
CUB - Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok, Thailand
EMKSU – Evermann Museum Kasan State University, Kasan, Russia
IRSNB – Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Science, Brussels
KIZ – Kuming Institute of Zoology, Kunming, China
MCZ- Museum of Comparative Zoology, Harvard, Cambridge, MA, U.S.A.
MNHN (MNHP) – Museum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France
MSNG (MCG) – Museo Civico di Storia Naturale de Genova, Italy
MTD (MTKD) – Museum für Tierkunde, Staatliche Naturhistorische Sammlungen, Dresden, Germany
MZB – Museum Zoologicum Bogoriense, Bogor (now at Cibinong), Indonesia
NMSL – Natural History Museum Colombo, Sri Lanka
NHMW – Naturhistorisches Museum Wien, Vienna, Austria
NMV – National Museum of Victoria, Melbourne, Australia
NHRM – Naturhistoriska Riksmuseet, Stockholm, Sweden
NTM – Northern Territory Museum, Darwin, Australia
QM – Queensland Museum, Brisbane, Australia
PNM – Philippine National Museum, Manila, Philippines
RCSOM – Royal College of Surgeons of England Museum, London
RMNH - Rijksmuseum van Natuurlijke Historie, Leiden, Netherlands
SAMA – South Australian Museum, Adelaide, Australia
SMF – Forschungsinstitut und Natur Museum Senckenberg, Frankfurt, Germany
WAM – Western Australian Museum, Perth, Australia
ZFMK – Zoologisches Forschungsinstitut und Museum Alexander König, Bonn, Germany
ZMB – Museum für Naturkunde der Humboldt Universität zu Berlin, Germany
ZMUC – Universitets Københaven Zoologisk Museum, Copenhagen, Denmark
ZMZ – Zoologisches Museum, Universität Zurich, Switzerland
ZSIC – Zoological Survey of India, Kolkata, India (formerly Indian Museum)

The definitions of the type categories Holotype, Syntype, Paratype, Lectotype and Neotype follow those given in the glossary and articles of the ICZN Code (ICZN, 1999).

In addition, I also use the following term: Iconotype - Some early 18th century species descriptions were done from paintings of live animals. More recently, some rare animals for which no museum

specimens existed were described accompanied by a photograph. Such pictorial types are termed iconotypes.

The synonymy in this paper is my own. I have deliberately omitted all *lapsa*, *nomina nuda*, etc., from the synonymy because these names are not available for use. The synonymy herein is limited to new descriptions. For a complete synonymy, reference should be had to Mertens (1963) and Böhme (2003).

Designation of a lectotype for *Monitor celebensis* (Schlegel, 1844) (= *V. salvator celebensis*)

Hermann Schlegel (1804-1884) was curator at the Rijksmuseum van Natuurlijke Historie in Leiden when he described *Monitor salvator celebensis*. In his description (1844), he did not designate a holotype. He had available to him in the museum at the time two specimens of water monitor from Sulawesi, RMNH 3176, a female from unknown locality on Sulawesi, collected by V. Delden (date unknown); and RMNH 3179, a male collected in 1841 near Manado, Sulawesi, by E.A. Forsten. With the publication of Koch et al. (2007) and recognition of more than one water monitor in Sulawesi, it seems wise to recognize a type for the common form in North Sulawesi.

I have chosen RMNH 3179 to designate as the lectotype for this taxon. This represents the common phase, with large spots, of the Celebes Water Monitor.

Fig.1. Lectotype of *Varanus salvator celebensis* (RMNH 3179) from Manado, Sulawesi, Indonesia

Designation of neotype for *Varanus kordensis*

The original type specimen in Dresden (MTKD) was destroyed in World War II. The destroyed holotype of *Varanus kordensis* was from the Kordo (=Biak), Schouten Archipelago, Papua, Indonesia, and the designated neotype is also from Biak, Indonesia. Since both specimens were collected on the same small island, it is safe to assume that both represent the same taxon. Sprackland (1991) thought *kordensis* to be a “minor color variation” of *V. prasinus*. Except for a

live specimen in the Oklahoma City Zoo, it is not clear how many *kordensis* he examined. Jacobs (2002) examined four specimens in Germany and the Netherlands and concluded that the taxon is valid. He also had at his disposal several live specimens. Since neither of these authors had access to the type specimen, by then destroyed, it seems prudent to designate a new type from the original location in this catalog.

Neotype: RMNH 21009, female, Biak, Indonesia; don. L. van der Hammer, 1953.

Diagnosis: *Varanus kordensis* is distinguished from all other members of the *V. prasinus* group by the following combination of character states: (1) slender, arboreal body form (70-80 cm total length); (2) tail length almost twice body length; (3) nuchal scales keeled; color pattern reticulum of dark ocelli overlain on ground color, including legs and tail; (4) color yellow-olive to dark green; (5) midbody scales average 89, across the head 34; (6) light brown bands across belly.

Description of neotype (Figs. 2, 3 & 4):

Habitus very slender. Total length 750 (250+500) mm. Nostril oval and closer to tip of snout than to eye. Canthal ridge weakly expressed. Snout pointed. Nasal region, slightly swollen, with a median, shallow groove. Supraoculars enlarged, 5/5. Pineal organ covered by a slightly enlarged, oval scale, with whitish blotch in the center. Scales on nape smooth, nearly round, gradually becoming oval and keeled on the back. Gular scales smooth and round, becoming oval and smooth on the neck. Ventral scales elongated. Dorsal sides of limbs with oval and weakly keeled scales, ventral scales mostly rounded and smooth. Prehensile tail nearly circular. Caudal scales keeled dorsally and ventrally.

Fig. 2. Neotype of *Varanus kordensis* (RMNH 21009), dorsal view.

Scale counts, measurements and proportion indices of the neotype are taken from Brandenburg (1983) as follows: (1) number of scales counted in straight line across head between corners of mouth = 38; (2) number of scales counted around base of tail = 47; (3) scales counted around midbody = 86; (4) number of transverse ventral rows of scales from gular fold to last uninterrupted row at anterior border of hind limbs = 72; (5) number of dorsal transverse rows of scales from posterior dorsal points of ear to gular fold then to anterior border of hind limbs = 105; (6) number of supralabials = 43; (7) number of scales around neck anterior to gular fold = 82; (8) number of ventral scales from chin to gular fold = 62; (9) relative length of tail compared to snout-vent length = 2.00; (10) position of nostril between eye and tip of snout = 1.16; (11) index for reduction of scales along tail = 2.04; (12) comparison of dorsal and ventral scale rows = 1.46; (13) position of

nostril - point on nostril to point of snout = 1.80; (14) relative length of head compared to width = 1.83; (15) relative length of head compared to depth = 2.75.

Color (in preservative): Dorsum of head blackish with pale bluish-gray scales. Neck, back, limbs and base of tail with a black reticulatum and pattern of pale (=green in life) rosettes. Lower parts dark gray with brownish tinge. Snout and lips yellowish. Eyelids yellowish.

Fig. 3. Neotype of *Varanus kordensis* (RMNH 21009), ventral view

Fig. 4. Neotype of *Varanus kordensis* (RMNH 21009), lateral aspect of head

GENUS

Varanus Merrem, 1820, p. 58. Type species: *Varanus varius* White, 1790, by subsequent designation of Gray, 1827.

Synonymy:

Monitor Lichtenstein, 1818, p. 66. Type species: *Monitor niloticus* (= *V. niloticus*). Name preoccupied by *Monitor* Blainville, 1816, with *Monitor teguixin* (= *Tupinambis meriani*) as type species.

Varanus Rafinesque, 1815, p.150, Palermo (*nomen nudum*).

Psammosaurus Fitzinger, 1826, pp. 21, 51. Type species: *Psammosaurus griseus* (Daudin, 1803), by monotypy.

Polydaedalus Wagler, 1830, p. 164. Type species: *Polydaedalus niloticus* (Linnaeus, 1766), by subsequent designation of Fitzinger, 1843.

Hydrosaurus Wagler, 1830, p. 164. Type species: *Hydrosaurus bivittatus* (Kuhl, 1820), by subsequent designation of Fitzinger, 1843.

Empagusia Gray, 1838, p. 393. Type species: *Empagusia flavescens* (Hardwicke & Gray, 1827), by monotypy.

Odatria Gray, 1838, p. 394. Type species: *Odatria punctata* (= *V. tristis*) (Schlegel, 1838), by monotypy.

Pantherosaurus Fitzinger, 1843, p. 19. Type species: *Pantherosaurus gouldii* (Gray, 1838), by original designation.

Cylindrurus Fitzinger, 1843, p. 19. Type species: *Cylindrurus punctatus* (= *V. tristis*) (Schlegel, 1838), by original designation.

Agalmatosaurus Fitzinger, 1843, p. 19. Type species: *Agalmatosaurus timorensis* (Gray, 1831), by original designation.

Euprepiosaurus Fitzinger, 1843, p. 19. Type species: *Euprepiosaurus chlorostigma* (Gray in Griffith 1831) (= *V. indicus*), by original designation.

Pachysaurus Fitzinger, 1843, p. 20. Type species: *Pachysaurus albigularis* (Daudin, 1802), by original designation.

Rhinoptyon Fitzinger, 1843, p. 20. Type species: *Varanus exanthematicus* (Bosc, 1792), by original designation.

Regenia Gray, 1845, p. 8. Type species: *Regenia albigularis* (Daudin, 1802), by original designation.

Placovaranus Fjérvary, 1927, p. 284. Type species: *Varanus komodoensis* Ouwens, 1912, by original designation.

Indovaranus Mertens 1942, 462: 16; 466: 240. Type species: *Varanus bengalensis* (Daudin, 1802), by original designation.

Dendrovaranus Mertens 1942, 462: 16; 466: 241. Type species: *Varanus rudicollis* (Gray, 1845), by original designation.

Tectovaranus Mertens 1942, 462: 16; 466: 242. Type species: *Varanus dumerili* (Schlegel, 1837), by original designation.

Philippinosaurus Mertens 1959, p. 228. Type species: *Varanus grayi* Boulenger, 1885 (= *Varanus olivaceus* Hallowell, 1856), by original designation.

Papusaurus Mertens 1962, p. 331. Type species: *Varanus salvadorii* (Peters & Doria, 1878), by original designation.

Titanzius Wells & Wellington, 1985, p. 22. Type species: *Hydrosaurus giganteus* Gray, 1845, by original designation.

Aspetosaurus Wells & Wellington, 1985, p. 20. Type species: *Varanus spenceri* Lucas & Frost, 1903, by original designation.

Worrellisaurus Wells & Wellington, 1984, p. 22. Type species: *Varanus acanthurus* Boulenger, 1885, by original designation.

Sotosaurus Ziegler & Böhme, 1997, p. 176. Type species: *Varanus salvator* (Laurenti, 1768), by original designation.

SPECIES LIST

Varanus acanthurus Boulenger, 1885

Varanus acanthurus acanthurus Boulenger, 1885

Varanus acanthurus acanthurus Boulenger, 1885, p. 8. Type locality: northwest coast of Australia. Holotype: BMNH 1945.8.30.97, by monotypy.

Distribution: northern and western Australia, from vicinity of Broome to Gulf of Carpentaria.

Varanus acanthurus brachyurus Sternfeld, 1919

Varanus acanthurus brachyurus Sternfeld, 1919, p. 78. Type locality: Hermannsburg, Finke River, central Australia [Northern Territory]. Lectotype: SMF 11640, by designation of Mertens (1967).

Distribution: arid and seasonally dry regions of Queensland and eastern Northern Territory.

Varanus acanthurus insulanicus Mertens, 1958

Varanus acanthurus insulanicus Mertens, 1958, p. 233. Type locality: Groote Eylandt, Gulf of Carpentaria, Northern Territory, Australia. Holotype: AM R11037, by original designation.

Distribution: Groote Eylandt and Marchinbar islands, Gulf of Carpentaria, Australia.

Varanus albigularis (Daudin, 1802)

Varanus albigularis albigularis (Daudin, 1802)

Tupinambis albigularis Daudin, 1802, p. 72. Type locality: unknown. Holotype: MNHN 6513, by original designation.

Synonyms:

Varanus gillii Smith, 1831, p. 16. Type locality: mountains of Graaf-Reinet and the Orange River. Types described from captives possessed by W. Gill, apparently not preserved.

Varanus exanthematicus capensis Schlegel, 1844, p. 71, pl. 22, Figs. 3 & 4. Type locality: Cape of Good Hope, South Africa. Syntypes: RMNH 40286, RMNH 40288.

Distribution: Namibia, Botswana, South Africa, Zimbabwe, Mozambique and Zambia.

Varanus albigularis angolensis Schmidt, 1933

Varanus albigularis angolensis Schmidt, 1933, p. 10. Type locality: Gauca, Biha, Angola. Holotype: CM S5967, by original designation.

Distribution: Angola and adjacent parts of the Democratic Republic of the Congo and Namibia.

Varanus albigularis microstictus Boettger, 1893

Varanus microstictus Boettger, 1893, p. viii. Type locality: Ethiopia. Holotype: SMF 11545, by original designation.

Synonym:

Varanus exanthematicus ionidesi Laurent 1964, pp. 1-5. Type locality: Kilwa, southern Tanzania. Holotype: MCZ 55470, by original designation.

Distribution: East Africa, from southern Ethiopia, Sudan and Somalia, south through Kenya, Tanzania, Uganda, to northern Mozambique.

Varanus auffenbergi Sprackland, 1999

Varanus auffenbergi Sprackland, 1999, p. 22. Type locality: Roti Island, near Timor. Holotype: AMNH 143812, by original designation.

Distribution: Roti Island, west of Timor, Indonesia.

Varanus baritji King & Horner, 1987

Varanus baritji King & Horner, 1987, pp. 73-79. Type locality: Mirrngadja, Northern Territory, rock outcrop in Arafura Swamp. Holotype: NTM R13192, by original designation.

Distribution: Arnhem Land and vicinity, Northern Territory, Australia

Varanus beccarii (Doria, 1874)

Monitor beccarii Doria, 1874, p. 331. Type locality: Wokam, Aru Islands. Holotype: ZMB 7993, by monotypy.

Distribution: Aru Islands, Indonesia.

Varanus bengalensis (Daudin, 1802)

Tupinambis bengalensis Daudin, 1802, p. 36. Type locality: Bengal (India). Lectotype: MNHN 2179, by designation of Guibé (1954).

Synonyms:

Tupinambis cepedianus Daudin, 1802, p. 43. Type locality: unknown. Syntype: MNHN 2198.

Lacerta argus Daudin, 1802, p. 117. Type locality: unknown. Type: MHNP, lost.

Varanus punctatus Merrem, 1820, p. 59. Type locality: Bengal, India. No type designated.

Varanus taraguira Merrem, 1820, p. 59. Type locality: unknown. No type designated.

Monitor gemmatus Guérin-Méneville, 1829, pl. 3. Type locality: India. Type: MNHN. No specimen recognized.

Monitor heraldicus Gray, in Griffith, 1831, p. 27. Type locality: Bengal, India. MNHN, original number 1501, subsequently lost.

Monitor inornatus Schlegel, 1839, p. 72. Type locality: unknown. Holotype: RMNH, lost.

Varanus bibronii Blyth, 1842, p. 869. Type locality: unknown. Type: lost (Das, pers. comm.).

Varanus lunatus Gray, 1845, p. 10. Type locality: India. Holotype: BMNH I.10a(41.950), by monotypy.

Varanus irrawadicus Yang & Li, 1987, p. 60. Type locality: Wanding Valley, Yunnan, China. Holotype: KIZ 86001, by original designation.

Distribution: southeastern Iran, eastern Afghanistan, Sri Lanka, Pakistan, India, Bangladesh, Burma, Nepal and extreme southern Yunnan (China).

Varanus boehmei Jacobs, 2003

Varanus boehmei Jacobs, 2003, p. 66. Type locality: Waigeo Island, Papua, Indonesia. Holotype: ZFMK 77837, by original designation.

Distribution: Waigeo Island, Papua province, Indonesia.

Varanus bogerti Mertens, 1950

Varanus prasinus bogerti Mertens, 1950, p. 3. Type locality: Fergusson Island, D'Entrecasteaux Archipelago, Papua New Guinea. Holotype: AMNH 41639, by original designation.

Distribution: Kiriwina Island in the Trobriand group, Fergusson and Normanby islands in the D'Entrecasteaux group and Misima Island in the Louisiade Archipelago, all in Milne Bay province, Papua New Guinea.

Varanus brevicauda Boulenger, 1898

Varanus brevicauda Boulenger, 1898, pp. 916, 920. Type locality: Sherlock River, Nickol Bay, Western Australia. Lectotype: BMNH 1946.8.30.46, designated by Wells and Wellington (1985).

Distribution: arid regions of Western Australia, southern Northern Territory, northwest South Australia and extreme western Queensland.

Varanus bushi Aplin, Fitch & King, 2006

Varanus bushi Aplin, Fitch & King, 2006, p. 24. Type locality: Marandoo, Western Australia. Holotype: WAM R108999, by original designation.

Distribution: Pilbara Uplands, Western Australia.

Varanus caerulivirens Ziegler, Böhme & Philipp, 1999

Varanus caerulivirens Ziegler, Böhme & Philipp, 1999, p. 46. Type locality: Halmahera, Moluccas, Indonesia. Holotype: ZFMK 68874, by original designation.

Distribution: Halmahera and Morotai islands, Maluku province, Indonesia.

Varanus caudolineatus Boulenger, 1885

Varanus caudolineatus Boulenger, 1885, p. 324. Type locality: Champion Bay, Western Australia. Holotype: BMNH 64.7.22.3, by monotypy.

Distribution: Coast and interior of central Western Australia.

Varanus cerambonensis Philipp, Böhme & Ziegler, 1999

Varanus cerambonensis Philipp, Böhme & Ziegler, 1999, p. 281. Type locality: Laimu, south coast of Seram, Moluccas, Indonesia. Holotype: ZFMK 70617, by original designation.

Distribution: Seram, Ambon, Buru, Obi and Banda Islands, Indonesia.

Varanus cumingi Martin, 1838

Varanus cumingi Martin, 1838, p. 69. Type locality: Mindanao, Philippines. Lectotype: BMNH 1946.8.31.5, by designation of Koch et al (2007).

Distribution: southern Philippines: Mindanao, Leyte, Samar, Bohol and Basilan islands.

Varanus doreanus (Meyer, 1874)

Monitor kalabeck Lesson, in Duperey, 1830, p. 52. Type locality: Offack Bay, northern coast of Waigeo Island, Papua, Indonesia. (*nomen dubium*). No type.

Monitor doreanus Meyer, 1874, p. 130. Type locality: Doreh, Berou Peninsula, northwest New Guinea. Holotype destroyed in World War II. Neotype: ZFMK 52922, by designation of Böhme, Horn & Ziegler (1994).

Distribution: Papua New Guinea, Indonesia (Papua, Aru, Salawati, Biak, Yapen, Mansinam) and the Iron Range, Cape York, Australia.

Varanus dumerilii (Schlegel, 1839)

Monitor dumerilii Schlegel, 1839, p. 78. Type locality: Banjarmasin, southeast Borneo, Kalimantan, Indonesia. Holotype: RMNH 3168, by monotypy.

Synonyms:

Varanus macrolepis Blanford, 1881, p. 239. Type locality: Tenasserim, Burma. Holotype: ZSIC 11482, by monotypy.

Varanus heteropholis Boulenger, 1892, p. 506. Type locality: Mt. Dulit, upper Baram River, Sarawak, Malaysia. Holotype: BMNH 92.6.3.1, by monotypy.

Distribution: Burma, southern Thailand, Malaysia, Indonesia (Batu, Sumatra, Bangka, Kalimantan, Riau, Belitung), Sarawak and Sabah in West Malaysia.

Varanus eremius Lucas & Frost, 1895

Varanus eremius Lucas & Frost, 1895, p. 267. Type locality: Idracowra, Northern Territory, Australia. Holotype: NMV D9136, by monotypy.

Distribution: central and coastal Western Australia through the deserts of South Australia and Northern Territory to southwestern Queensland.

Varanus exanthematicus (Bosc, 1792)

Lacerta exanthematica Bosc, 1792, p. 25. Type locality: Senegal River. Holotype: MNHN, specimen lost; Pl. v, fig. 3, p. 25, *Actes de la Société d'Histoire Naturelle de Paris*.

Synonyms:

Varanus ocellatus Heyden, in Rüppell, 1830, p. 21. Type locality: Kordofan, Sudan. Holotype: SMF 11544, by monotypy.

Distribution: from southern Mauritania to Nigeria in West Africa and then east to the Sudan-Ethiopian borderland.

Varanus finschi Böhme, Horn & Ziegler, 1994

Varanus doreanus finschi Böhme, Horn & Ziegler, 1994, p. 137. Type locality: Blanche Bay, New Britain, Bismarck Archipelago, Papua New Guinea. Holotype: ZFMK 26347, by original designation.

Distribution: New Britain and New Ireland in the Bismarck Archipelago and Huon Peninsula, Papua New Guinea; Kei Islands, Indonesia (doubtful allocation); Cape York, Australia (doubtful).

Varanus flavescens (Hardwicke & Gray, 1827)

Monitor flavescens Hardwicke & Gray, 1827, p. 226. Type locality: Calcutta, West Bengal, India. Holotype (iconotype): pl. 60, 61, *Illustrations of Indian Zoology*, Hardwicke, 1829.

Synonyms:

Varanus picquotii Duméril & Bibron, 1836, p. 485. Type locality: Bengal, India. Syntypes: MHNP 8339, MHNP 2181.

Varanus russelli Heyden, in Rüppell, 1830, p. 23. Type locality: Bengal, India. Holotype: SMF 11546, by monotypy.

Monitor exanthematicus indicus Schlegel, 1844, p. 71. Type locality: Bengal, India. Holotype: RMNH 3158, by monotypy.

Distribution: flood plains of Indus, Ganges and Brahmaputra rivers, Pakistan, India, Nepal and Bangladesh.

Varanus flavirufus Mertens, 1958

Varanus gouldii flavirufus Mertens, 1958, p. 250. Type locality: Bat Caves, south of Alice Springs, Northern Territory, Australia. Holotype: SMF 53271, by original designation.

Distribution: sandy deserts of western Queensland and northwestern New South Wales, to the Great Victorian and Great Sandy Deserts, Western Australia; as far north as the Tanami Desert, Northern Territory, and as far west as the coast between Dampier Land and Exmouth Gulf.

Varanus giganteus (Gray 1845)

Hydrosaurus giganteus Gray, 1845, p. 13. Type locality: north coast of Australia. Holotype: BMNH 1.22a, by monotypy.

Distribution: arid parts of Australia, from western Queensland to the coast of Western Australia.

Varanus gilleni Lucas & Frost, 1895

Varanus gilleni Lucas & Frost, 1895, p. 266. Type locality: between Glen Edith and Deering Creek, Northern Territory, Australia. Holotype: NMV D11759, by monotypy.

Distribution: deserts of South Australia, Northern Territory and Western Australia to the northwestern coast.

Varanus glauerti Mertens, 1957

Varanus timorensis glauerti Mertens, 1957, p. 183. Type locality: Wotjulum, West Kimberley, Western Australia. Holotype: WAM R12337, by original designation.

Distribution: Kimberley region of Western Australia and adjacent Northern Territory. Isolated population in northwestern Arnhem Land and adjacent Kakadu National Park, Northern Territory.

Varanus glebopalma Mitchell, 1955

Varanus glebopalma Mitchell, 1955, p. 389. Type locality: south end of Lake Hubert, Northern Territory. Holotype: SAMA R3222, by original designation.

Distribution: northeastern Western Australia, northern Northern Territory and northwestern Queensland.

Varanus gouldii (Gray, 1838)

Hydrosaurus gouldii Gray, 1838, p. 394. Type locality: Karakatta, Perth, Western Australia. Neotype: BMNH 1997.1, designated by ICZN, Opinion 1948 (2000).

Synonym:

Pantherosaurus barryjonesi Wells & Wellington, 1985, p. 21. Type locality: Hillston to Griffith Rd., New South Wales. Holotype: AM R1169971, by original designation.

Distribution: southwestern Western Australia (Shark Bay to Cape Naturaliste), east to Nullarbor Plain; northern Australia (Dampier Land, Western Australia, to Barkly Tableland, Northern Territory); western Queensland; eastern and central New South Wales.

Varanus griseus (Daudin, 1803)

Varanus griseus griseus (Daudin, 1803)

Tupinambis griseus Daudin, 1803, p. 352. Type locality: Egypt. Holotype: MHNP, lost.

Synonyms:

Varanus scincus Merrem, 1820, p. 59. Type locality: Egypt. No type designated,

Tupinambis arenarius Geoffroy, 1827, p. 123. Type locality: Egypt. Type: MHNP, not found.

Varanus terrestris Schinz, 1834, p. 94. Type locality: Cairo, Egypt. Type: ZMZ, not found.

Psammosaurus arabicus Hemprich & Ehrenberg, 1899, p. 3. Type locality: Arabia. Holotype: ZMB, lost

Distribution: deserts of North Africa (Morocco and Mauritania east to Egypt and Sudan); southeastern Turkey, Syria, Lebanon, Israel, Jordan, Iraq and the Arabian Peninsula.

Varanus griseus caspius (Eichwald, 1831)

Psammosaurus caspius Eichwald, 1831, p. 190. Type locality: Dardsha Peninsula, southeastern coast of Caspian Sea, Turkmenistan. Holotype: EMKSU, not located.

Distribution: deserts of central Asia: northern Iran, Afghanistan, southwest Pakistan, Turkmenistan, southern Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan.

***Varanus griseus koniecznyi* Mertens, 1954**

Varanus griseus koniecznyi Mertens, 1954, p. 355. Type locality: Korangee, near Karachi, Pakistan. Holotype: SMF 46784, by original designation.

Distribution: acacia woodland and desert scrubland of eastern Pakistan and northwestern India.

***Varanus indicus* (Daudin, 1802)**

Tupinambis indicus Daudin, 1802, p. 46. Type locality: Ambon, Maluku, Indonesia. Holotype: MHNP, lost. Neotype: ZFMK 70650, by designation of Philipp, Böhme, & Ziegler (1999).

Synonyms:

Varanus guttatus Merrem, 1820, p. 58. Type locality: Ambon, Maluku, Indonesia. (*nomen dubium*). No type.

Monitor douarrha Lesson, in Duperey, 1830, p. 53. Type locality: Port Praslin, New Ireland, Bismarck Archipelago (*nomen dubium*). No type.

Varanus indicus rouxi Mertens, 1926, p. 276. Type locality: Durdjela, Wammer, Aru Islands. Holotype: SMF 11583, by original designation.

Monitor chlorostigma Gray, in Griffith, 1831, p. 26. Type locality: Rawack (Manuran) Island, north of Waigeo, Papua, Indonesia. Holotype: MNHN 2202, by monotypy, possibly lost.

Varanus tsukamotoi Kishida, 1929, p. 14. Type locality: Saipan, Northern Mariana Islands. Type unknown.

Distribution: Indonesia (Talaud, Ternate, Bacan, Morotai, Halmahera, Obi, Buru, Ambon, Saparua, Haruku, Seram, Nusa Laut, Letri, Tanimbar, Banda, Gorong, Kei, Aru, Gebe, Kawe, Waigeo, Salawati, Papua, Biak, Numfor, Yapen); Papua New Guinea (including Bismarck Archipelago and Bougainville); Solomon Islands (Shortland, Rendova, Ysabel, New Georgia, Russell, Guadalcanal, Nggela, Savo, Malaita, San Cristobal, Agi, Olu Malau, Kolombangara, Giza); Palau (Babeldaob, Oreor, Ngeaur, Ngcheangel); Caroline Islands (Ifalik, Kosrae, Pohnpei, Yap, Ulithi, Truk); Mariana Islands (Guam, Rota, Saipan); Bonin Islands; Marshall Islands (Eniwetok); Australia (eastern Cape York Peninsula, islands of Torres Strait and coastal Arnhem Land).

***Varanus jobiensis* Ahl, 1932**

Varanus indicus jobiensis Ahl, 1932, p. 17: 892. Type locality: Yapen, Papua, Indonesia. Holotype: ZMB 34106, by original designation.

Synonym:

Varanus karlschmidti Mertens, 1951, p. 467. Type locality: Marienberg, Sepik River, Papua New Guinea. Holotype: FMNH 14107, by original designation.

Distribution: Indonesia: Salawati, Batanta, Yapen, Papua, Waigeo; western Papua New Guinea.

***Varanus juxtindicus* Böhme, Philipp & Ziegler, 2002**

Varanus juxtindicus Böhme, Philipp & Ziegler, 2002, p. 17. Type locality: Lake Tenggano, near Niupani, Rennell Island, Solomon Islands. Holotype: ZMUC R E 605, by original designation.

Distribution: Known only from Rennell Island, southernmost of the Solomons.

***Varanus keithhornei* (Wells & Wellington, 1985)**

Odatia keithhornei Wells & Wellington, 1985, p. 21. Type locality: Buthen Buthen, Nesbit River, Cape York Peninsula, Queensland, Australia. Holotype: QM J31566, by original designation.

Synonym:

Varanus teriae Sprackland, 1991, p. 570. Type locality: Buthen Buthen, Nesbit River, Cape York Peninsula, Queensland. Holotype: QM J31566, by original designation.

Distribution: Iron Range and McIlwraith Range, Cape York Peninsula, northern Queensland, Australia.

Varanus kingorum Storr, 1980

Varanus kingorum Storr, 1980, p. 268. Type locality: 10 km west north west of Timber Creek (15°37'S, 130°23'E), Northern Territory, Australia. Holotype: WAM R60374, by original designation.

Distribution: east Kimberley region on the northern border of Western Australia and Northern Territory.

Varanus komodoensis Ouwens, 1912

Varanus komodoensis Ouwens, 1912, p. 1. Type locality: Komodo Island, Lesser Sunda Islands, Indonesia. Syntypes: MZB Rept. 946; RMNH 35517.

Distribution: Komodo, Padar, Rinca and parts of Flores islands, Lesser Sunda region, Indonesia.

Varanus kordensis (Meyer, 1874)

Monitor kordensis Meyer, 1874, p. 131. Type locality: Kordo (=Biak), Schouten Archipelago, Papua, Indonesia. Holotype: MTKD, destroyed in World War II. Neotype RMNH 21009, designated by De Lisle, 2009, pp. 10, 11 & 12 (this publication).

Distribution: Biak Island, Papua Province, Indonesia (probably also on neighbouring Supiori Island).

Varanus lirungensis Koch, Arida, Schmitz, Böhme & Ziegler, 2009

Varanus lirungensis Koch, Arida, Schmitz, Böhme & Ziegler, 2009, p. 29–40. Type locality: near Lirung, Pulau Salibabu, Talaud Islands, Indonesia. Holotype: MZB Lac. 5178, by original designation.

Distribution: Talaud Islands, Indonesia.

Varanus mabintang Gaulke & Curio, 2001

Varanus mabintang Gaulke & Curio, 2001, p. 277. Type locality: South Pandan Forest, Pandan municipality, Antique Province, northwest Panay Island, Philippines. Holotype: PNM 7272, by original designation.

Distribution: northwestern Panay Peninsula and Western Panay Range, Panay Island, Philippines.

Varanus macraei Böhme & Jacobs, 2001

Varanus macraei Böhme & Jacobs, 2001, p. 7. Type locality: Batanta Island, Papua, Indonesia. Holotype: ZFMK 74558, by original designation.

Distribution: Batanta Island, Papua province, Indonesia.

Varanus marmoratus (Wiegmann, 1834)

Hydrosaurus marmoratus Wiegmann, 1834, p. 446. Type locality: San Mateo, Luzon, Philippines. Lectotype: ZMB 470, by designation of Mertens (1942b).

Synonyms:

Monitor bivittatus philippensis Schlegel, 1844, p. 77. Type locality: Jalajalo, Luzon, Philippines. Holotype: RMNH 3173, by monotypy.

Varanus salvator philippensis Deraniyagala, 1944, p. 61. Type locality: Luzon, Philippines. Holotype: MNHN 1530, by original designation.

Distribution: Philippines: Luzon, Polillo, Ticao, Calamian, Sojon, Mindoro, Culion, Calauit, Balabac, Palawan, Sulu Archipelago (Bongao, Sanga Sanga, Siasi, Jolo, Sibutu, Tawi-Tawi), Semirara Islands (Caluya, Panagatan III, Semirara), Babuyan Islands (Camiguin).

Varanus melinus Böhme & Ziegler, 1997

Varanus melinus Böhme & Ziegler, 1997, p. 26. Type locality: (in error) Obi Island, Maluku, Indonesia. Holotype: ZFMK 65737, by original designation.

Distribution: Bowokan, Taliabu, Mangole, Lifamatola islands, Indonesia.

Varanus mertensi Glauert, 1951

Varanus mertensi Glauert, 1951, p. 14. Type locality: Moola Bulla Cattle Station, near Halls Creek, East Kimberley, Western Australia. Holotype: WAM R5819, by original designation.

Synonym:

Varanus bulliwallah Worrell, 1956, p. 201. Type locality: Bulliwallah station on the Belyando River, Queensland, Australia. Holotype: AM R14810, by monotypy.

Distribution: northern Australia, from Broome in Western Australia east to Cape York, Queensland.

Varanus mitchelli Mertens, 1958

Varanus mitchelli Mertens, 1958, p. 256. Type locality: 5 miles west of Oenpelli, Northern Territory, Australia. Holotype: SAMA R3230, by original designation.

Distribution: Kimberley region, Western Australia, east to extreme northwestern Queensland.

Varanus nebulosus (Gray, 1851)

Monitor nebulosus Gray, in Griffith, 1851, p. 27. Type locality: Java, Indonesia. Holotype: MNHN 8258, by monotypy.

Synonym:

Varanus vietnamensis Yang & Liu 1994, p. 11. Type locality: northern Vietnam. Holotype: KIZ 92001, by original designation.

Distribution: southern Burma, Thailand, west Malaysia, Singapore, Vietnam, Cambodia, Laos, Indonesia (Sumatra, Java, Anambas, Riau, western Kalimantan).

Varanus niloticus (Linnaeus, 1766)

Lacerta nilotica Linnaeus, 1766, p. 369. Type locality: Egypt. Syntypes: NHRM 119 and NHRM 9185.

Synonyms:

Stellio saurus Laurenti, 1768, p. 56. Type locality: unknown. Holotype (iconotype): A. Seba, *Locupletissimi rerum naturalium thesauri accurata descriptio et iconibus artificiosissimis expressio per universam physices historiam*, II, pl. 105.1.

Lacerta capensis Sparman, 1783, p. 749. Type locality: Hinterbruyntjes Cave, Cape province, South Africa. Type: NHRM, lost.

Tupinambis stellatus Daudin, 1802, p. 59. Type locality: Senegal. Syntype: MNHN 8261.

Monitor pulcher Leach, in Bowdich, 1819, p. 493. Type locality: Fantee, Ghana. Syntype: BMNH 1946.8.30.98.

Monitor elegans senegalensis Schlegel, 1844, p. 76. Type locality: Senegal. Syntypes: RMNH 40289 and RMNH 40290.

Distribution: Senegal east to Somalia, along the Nile in Sudan as far as Qena, Egypt; south through most of the continent to South Africa.

Varanus nuchalis (Günther, 1872)

Hydrosaurus nuchalis Günther, 1872, p. 145. Type locality: Philippines. Holotype: BMNH 1946.9.1.17, by monotypy.

Distribution: Philippines: Boracay, Negros, Guimaras, Cebu, Panay, Masbate, Sibuyan, Siquijor, Ticao Islands.

Varanus olivaceus Hallowell, 1856

Varanus olivaceus Hallowell, 1856, p. 150. Type locality: Manila, Luzon, Philippines. Holotype: ANSP 9916, by monotypy.

Synonym:

Varanus grayi Boulenger, 1885, p. 312. Type locality: Philippines. Holotype: BMNH 1946.8.30.98, by monotypy.

Distribution: Philippines: southern Luzon, Catanduanes, Polillo Islands.

Varanus ornatus (Daudin, 1803)

Tupinambis ornatus Daudin, 1803, p. 353. Type locality: Malimbe, Cameroon. Holotype: MNHN 7471, by monotypy.

Distribution: western and eastern Guinean forests, Nigerian and Congolian lowland forests of Guinea, Sierra Leone, Liberia, Côte d'Ivoire, Nigeria, Cameroon, Gabon, Congo, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Central African Republic.

Varanus panoptes Storr, 1980

Varanus panoptes panoptes Storr, 1980

Varanus panoptes panoptes Storr, 1980, p. 273. Type locality: Lake Argyle (16°3'S, 128°47'E), Western Australia. Holotype: WAM R44792, by original designation.

Distribution: Kimberley region of Western Australia across northern Australia to Cape York, south through most of Queensland. Occurs on several islands off the Queensland coast.

Varanus panoptes horni Böhme, 1988

Varanus panoptes horni Böhme, 1988, p. 90. Type locality: Merauke, Papua, Indonesia. Holotype: ZFMK 19290, by original designation.

Distribution: southern New Guinea from near Port Moresby, Papua New Guinea, west to the Bomberai Peninsula, Papua, Indonesia. Also some islands in the Torres Strait.

Varanus panoptes rubidus Storr, 1980

Varanus panoptes rubidus Storr, 1980, p. 276. Type locality: Wilgie Mia (26°6'S, 117°42'E), 60 km north north west of Cue, Western Australia. Holotype: WAM R19132, by original designation.

Distribution: from near Broome to Fields Find, east into the Great Sandy and Great Victorian Deserts, Western Australia.

Varanus pilbarensis Storr, 1980

Varanus pilbarensis Storr, 1980. p. 278. Type locality: Chichester Range (22°3'S, 118°48'E), Western Australia. Holotype: WAM R39782, by original designation.

Distribution: Hamersley and Chichester Ranges, Pilbara region, Western Australia.

Varanus prasinus (Schlegel, 1839)

Monitor prasinus Schlegel, 1839, p. 78. Type locality: Fort du Bus, Triton Bay, southwest Papua, Indonesia. Syntypes: MCG 28723 and RMNH 4812.

Distribution: Indonesia: Salawati, Papua; Papua New Guinea (except southeast); Australia: islands in the Torres Strait.

Varanus primordius Mertens, 1942

Varanus acanthurus primordius Mertens, p. 41. Type locality: northern Australia. Holotype: ZMB 6204, by original designation.

Distribution: northern Northern Territory, Australia.

Varanus rainerguentheri Ziegler, Böhme & Schultz, 2007

Varanus rainerguentheri Ziegler, Böhme & Schultz, 2007, p. 110. Type locality: (in error) Jailolo, Halmahera Island, Maluku, Indonesia. Holotype: ZFMK 85404, by original designation.

Distribution: reported erroneously as Halmahera, Maluku, Indonesia. Real distribution is unknown.

Varanus reisingeri Eidenmüller & Wicker, 2005

Varanus reisingeri Eidenmüller & Wicker, 2005, p. 4. Type locality: Misool Island, Indonesia. Holotype: SMF 83679, by original designation.

Distribution: known only from Misool Island, Raja Ampat group, Papua province, Indonesia.

Varanus rosenbergi Mertens, 1957

Varanus gouldii rosenbergi Mertens, 1957, p. 18. Type locality: Monigup Pass, Stirling Range, Western Australia. Holotype: WAM R822, by original designation.

Synonym:

Pantherosaurus kuringai Wells & Wellington, 1985, p. 22. Type locality: Bobbin Head, Kuringai-Chase National Park, near Sydney, New South Wales, Australia. Holotype: AM R116991, by original designation.

Distribution: disjunct: southwestern tip of Western Australia to near Point Culver; southern Eyre Peninsula, Kangaroo Island, Sir Joseph Banks Islands and south-eastern part of South Australia; southwestern Victoria; mountains and coastal heaths of New South Wales.

Varanus rudicollis Gray, 1845

Varanus rudicollis Gray, 1845, p. 10. Type locality: unknown. Holotype: BMNH 1842.2.15.239, by monotypy.

Synonym:

Varanus scutigerulus Barbour, 1932, p. 1. Type locality: Kampung Ulu, Malam River, Sarawak, Malaysia. Holotype: MCZ R32264, by original designation.

Distribution: peninsular Burma and Thailand north to Tak province; Malaysia (east and west-Sarawak and Sabah); Indonesia (Riau, Sumatra, Bangka, Kalimantan).

Varanus salvadorii (Peters & Doria, 1876)

Monitor salvadorii Peters & Doria, 1876, p. 337. Type locality: Dorei, Papua, Indonesia. Holotype: MSNG 28726, by monotypy.

Distribution: lowlands of New Guinea, from the Kemp Welch River (southeast of Port Moresby) west to Vogelkop and Salawati Island (Papua, Indonesia); and then along the north coast to the Bewani Mountains, Papua New Guinea.

Varanus salvator (Laurenti, 1768)

Varanus salvator salvator (Laurenti, 1768)

Stellio salvator Laurenti, 1768, p. 56. Type locality: Sri Lanka. Iconotype: Fig. 2, Tab. 86, Tome II of Seba's "Thesaurus". Neotype: ZFMK 22092, by designation of Koch et al. (2007).

Synonym:

Varanus salvator kabaragoya Deraniyagala, 1947, p. 12. Type locality: Sri Lanka. Holotype: NMSL 40, by original designation.

Distribution: Sri Lanka.

Varanus salvator andamanensis Deraniyagala, 1944

Varanus salvator andamanensis Deraniyagala, 1944, p. 60. Type locality: Port Blair, South Andaman Island, Andaman Islands, India. Holotype: ZSIC 2176, by original designation.

Distribution: Andaman Islands, India.

Varanus salvator bivittatus (Kuhl, 1820)

Tupinambis bivittatus Kuhl, 1820, p. 125. Type locality: Java, Indonesia. Holotype: iconotype: Plate 30, fig. 2 in Seba's "Thesaurus", Tome II.

Synonyms:

Monitor nigricans Cuvier, 1829, p. 27. Type locality: Java. Syntypes: MNHN 8275 and 1195.

Monitor bivittatus javanica Schlegel, 1844, p. 76. Type locality: Java. Holotype: iconotype: Plate 30, fig. 2 in Seba's "Thesaurus", Tome II.

Varanus crocodilinus Owen, 1845, p. 265. Type locality: Java. Holotype: RCSOM/A 408.3, by monotypy.

Distribution: Indonesia: Java, Bawean, Bali, Lombok, Sumbawa, Komodo, Flores, Seribu, Karemanjawa, Kangean, Alor, Sumba, Bonerate, Wetar Islands.

Varanus salvator celebensis (Schlegel, 1844)

Monitor bivittatus celebensis Schlegel, 1844, p. x. Lectotype: RMNH 3179, by designation of De Lisle, 2009, p. 10 (this publication).

Distribution: Indonesia: Sulawesi, Sangihe Archipelago.

Varanus salvator komaini Nutphand, 1987

Varanus salvator komaini Nutphand, 1987, p. 51. Type locality: Amphoe, Langu, Satun province, Thailand. Holotype: CUB (unlabelled).

Distribution: southwestern Thailand and northwestern Malaysia.

Varanus salvator macromaculatus Deraniyagala, 1944

Varanus salvator macromaculatus Deraniyagala, 1944, p. 60. Type locality: Thailand. Lectotype: MNHN 871, by designation of Koch, et al. (2007).

Synonym:

Varanus salvator nicobariensis Deraniyagala, 1947, p. 12. Type locality: Nicobar Islands. Holotype: ZSIC 2147, by monotypy.

Distribution: northeastern India (West Bengal, Orissa, Assam), Bangladesh, Burma, Thailand, Cambodia, Laos, Vietnam, southern China (Yunnan, Kwantung, Kwangshi, Hong Kong, Hainan), Malaysia (incl. Sarawak and Sabah), Indonesia (Sumatra, Nias, Enggano, Bangka, Billiton, Kalimantan, Weh, Simeulie, Metawai, Anambas, Ponaitan, Tingil, Krakatau) and the Nicobar Islands. Introduced to Taiwan.

***Varanus scalaris* Mertens, 1941**

Varanus timorensis scalaris Mertens, 1941, p. 266. Type locality: Mission Beagle Bay, Dampier Land, northwest Australia. Holotype: SMF 32806, by original designation.

Synonyms:

Odatria kuranda Wells & Wellington, 1985, p. 21. Type locality: Kuranda (16°49'S, 145°38'E), Queensland. Holotype: AM R68820, by original designation.

Odatria pengilleyi Wells & Wellington, 1985, p. 21. Type locality: 40 km east of Pascoe River crossing (12°44'S, 143°10'E) (on road to Iron Range), Cape York, Queensland. Holotype: AM R94494, by original designation.

Distribution: nominate form is limited to Dampier Land, Western Australia; other forms range across northern Australia to Queensland.

***Varanus semiremex* Peters, 1869**

Varanus semiremex Peters, 1869, p. 65. Type locality: Cape York, Queensland, Australia. Holotype: ZMB 5776, by monotypy.

Synonym:

Varanus boulengeri Kinghorn, 1923, p. 135. Type locality: Coquet Island, Howick Group, Queensland. Holotype: AM R8083, by original designation.

Distribution: coastal Queensland. Northern form found on east coast of Cape York; southern form from southern Cape York to Gladstone and Rockhampton districts, Queensland. Also on west coast of Cape York: Albatross Bay to Mitchell River.

***Varanus similis* Mertens, 1958**

Varanus timorensis similis Mertens, 1958, p. 239. Type locality: Groote Eylandt, Northern Territory, Australia. Holotype: AM R10207, by original designation.

Distribution: nominate form is limited to Groote Eylandt, Arnhem Land and Kakadu, Northern Territory, Australia. Another form is found in southern New Guinea: from southeastern Papua, Indonesia, to Western Province, Papua New Guinea.

***Varanus spenceri* Lucas & Frost, 1903**

Varanus spenceri Lucas & Frost, 1903, p. 145. Type locality: Tablelands, 50 miles northeast of Tennant's Creek, Northern Territory. Holotype: NMV D12350, by original designation.

Synonym:

Varanus ingrami Boulenger 1906, p. 440. Type locality: Alexandria, Northern Territory, Australia. Holotype: BMNH 1946.8.31.6, by original designation.

Distribution: inland northwestern Queensland and eastern Northern Territory centred on Barkly Tableland.

Varanus spinulosus Mertens, 1941

Varanus indicus spinulosus Mertens, 1941, p. 269. Type locality: San Jorge Island, Solomon Islands. Holotype: NHMW 3709, by original designation.

Distribution: San Jorge and adjacent Isabel Islands; islets west of Morovo Lagoon, Solomon Islands. Southern Bougainville Island, Papua New Guinea.

Varanus storri Mertens, 1966

Varanus storri storri Mertens, 1966

Varanus storri storri Mertens, 1966, p. 437. Type locality: Charters Towers, Queensland, Australia. Holotype: SMF 59011, by original designation.

Distribution: vicinity Townsville, Queensland, to near Borrolloola, Northern Territory, Australia.

Varanus storri ocreatus Storr, 1980

Varanus storri ocreatus Storr, 1980, p. 283. Type locality: Argyle Downs airstrip (16°20'S, 128°46'E), now under Lake Argyle, Western Australia. Holotype: WAM R42717, by original designation.

Distribution: Kimberley region, Western Australia and adjacent Northern Territory.

Varanus telenesetes Sprackland, 1991

Varanus telenesetes Sprackland, 1991, p. 569. Type locality: Rossel Island (probably in error), Louisiade Archipelago, Papua New Guinea. Holotype: QM J1190, by original designation.

Distribution: presently unknown; not Rossel; possibly another island in the Archipelago (Kraus, pers. comm.).

Varanus timorensis (Gray, 1831)

Monitor timorensis Gray, 1831, p. 26. Type locality: Timor Island. Syntypes: MNHN 8278 and 8278A.

Distribution: Timor. Savu, Kisar Islands, Indonesia.

Varanus togianus (Peters, 1872)

Monitor togianus Peters, 1872, p. 582. Type locality: Timotto, Togian Island, Gulf of Tomini, Sulawesi, Indonesia. Lectotype: ZMB 7388, by designation of Mertens (1942b).

Distribution: Indonesia: Togian Islands; also Selayar Island and southwest peninsula of Sulawesi. The melanistic form found in the Sula Islands may also be this species.

Varanus tristis (Schlegel, 1838)

Varanus tristis tristis (Schlegel, 1838)

Monitor tristis Schlegel, 1838, p. 73. Type locality: Swan River, Western Australia. Holotype: RMNH 3858, by monotypy.

Synonym:

Odatria punctata Gray, 1838, p. 394. Type locality: Shark Bay, Western Australia. Holotype: BMNH i.32, by monotypy.

Distribution: most of Western Australia, southwestern Northern Territory and northwestern South Australia.

Varanus tristis orientalis Fry, 1913

Varanus punctatus orientalis Fry, 1913, p. 18. Type locality: Eidsvold, upper Burnett River, Queensland, Australia. Holotype: AM R5313, by original designation.

Synonym:

Varanus tristis centralis Mertens, 1957, p. 185. Type locality: Hermannsburg, Finke River, Northern Territory, Australia. Holotype: SMF 11632, by original designation.

Distribution: northern Western Australia, northern and eastern Northern Territory, most of Queensland, northwestern New South Wales, northeastern South Australia.

Varanus varius (White & Shaw, 1790)

Lacerta varia Shaw, in White, 1790, appendix, p. 253. Type locality: New South Wales. Holotype presumed lost.

Synonyms:

Tupinambis variegatus Daudin, 1802, p. 76. Type locality: Port Jackson, New South Wales, Australia. Syntype: MNHP 8287.

Varanus bellii Duméril & Bibron, 1836, p. 493. Type locality: Australia. Syntype: MNHP 8283.

Varanus mustelinus De Borre, 1870, p. 124. Type locality: unknown. Holotype: IRSNB 9422, by monotypy.

Distribution: northeastern coast of Queensland south through much of New South Wales to Victoria and South Australia.

Varanus yemenensis Böhme, Joger & Schätti, 1989

Varanus yemenensis Böhme, Joger & Schätti, 1989, p. 434. Type locality: Yemen. Holotype: ZFMK 46500, by original designation.

Distribution: southwestern Arabian Peninsula: Yemen and Saudi Arabia.

Varanus yuwonoi Harvey & Barker, 1998

Varanus yuwonoi Harvey & Barker, 1998, p. 36. Type locality: near Jailolo, Halmahera Island, Maluku, Indonesia. Holotype: UTA R41281, by original designation.

Distribution: known only from northwestern Halmahera, Maluku, Indonesia.

Varanus zugorum Böhme & Ziegler, 2005

Varanus zugorum Böhme & Ziegler, 2005, p. 52. Type locality: Kampung Pasir Putih, Jailolo dist., Halmahera Island, Maluku, Indonesia. Holotype: USNM 237439, by original designation.

Distribution: northern Halmahera Island, Maluku, Indonesia.

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